

ISic2973

I.Sicily inscription 2973

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near PalazzoloAcreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, (near) Palazzolo Acreide

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI175474

1. □
2. Καλήδεις
3. [— — — —]σαη [.]
4. [χρη]στῶς καὶ
5. [ἀμέ]μπτω [ς]
6. [ἔζη]σεν ἔτη
7. [—' — — — —]
8. □
- 9.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645328

PHI 175474

Bibliography

Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi. In Bernabó Brea, L. (eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.41

Führer, J., Schultze, V. 1907. Die altchristlichen Grabstätten Siziliens. Berlin. At 154 no.viii

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